

There are various possible sites on the uracil (1) for complex formation: (i) chelation between 5-substituent and 4-carbonyl, (ii) complexing on N-1, and (iii) complexing on N-3. Since the stability constant values of the uracil complexes were found to be higher than 5-bromouracil, 5-iodouracil and 5-nitouracil, this excludes the possibility of chelation involving bromo, iodo and nitro groups with 4-carbonyl groups. The possible complexing sites are now limited only to the nitrogens. For some metal ions, the stability constants of uracils are of the same order of magnitude as those of their corresponding deoxyuridines, the N-1 of which is blocked with a sugar molecule⁴. Moreover, the fact that the tendency of keto-enol tautomerism is more at N-3 than N-1 and complex formation is accompanied by the release of proton and there is an available proton on N-3 in 5-substituted uracils, makes N-3 as a complexing site most plausible. A comparison of stabilities of HgCl_2 and Be^{II} complexes show that Be^{II} complexes are more stable than those of HgCl_2 for all ligands studied. The higher stability of Be^{II} complexes may be due to smaller effective ionic radii compared to Hg^{II} . Further, Be^{II} being a hard acid tends to bond with hard bases favourably compared to soft acid Hg^{II} .

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Infrared, Thermal and X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Lanthanum Soaps

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Manuscript received 8 July 1986, revised 19 January 1987, accepted 19 May 1987

THE methods of preparation, properties and industrial applications of alkali, alkaline-earth and transition metal soaps have been thoroughly investigated but the studies of rare earth metal soaps¹⁻⁸ have remained almost unexplored in spite of their large applications in industries. The present work deals with the characteristics of lanthanum soaps in solid state using infrared, thermal and X-ray diffraction measurements.

Experimental

Lanthanum soaps were prepared, purified and analysed by the methods described in our earlier communication¹. The results for carbon, hydrogen and metal contents were found in agreement with the theoretically calculated values.

The infrared absorption spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The TGA was carried out at a constant heating rate of 10° min^{-1} (in a Mettler TG 50 instrument). The X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained with a Rich-Seifert 2002D diffractometer using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffraction angle, $2\theta = 3-40^\circ$, where θ is the Bragg angle. The wavelength of radiation was 1.542 Å.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra: The wavenumbers of important absorption maxima in the infrared spectra of lanthanum soaps (caprate and laurate) are assigned and compared with those of the corresponding fatty acids and sodium soaps. The absorption maxima near 2660-2650, 1700-1680, 1449-1430, 950-930, 690 and 550 cm^{-1} are associated with the localised carboxyl group of the acid molecules in the dimeric state and confirm the presence of hydrogen bonding between two molecules of fatty acid. The complete disappearance of the carbonyl frequency at 1700 cm^{-1} in the spectra of sodium and lanthanum soaps indicates that there is a complete resonance in the two C-O bonds of the soap molecule and the group has an ionic nature. The appearance of two bands of the carboxyl group corresponding to the symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate ion near 1450-1440 and 1650-1600 cm^{-1} in the spectra of sodium and lanthanum soaps instead of one band near 1700 cm^{-1} confirms

that these soaps possess ionised structure, and the metal-to-oxygen bonds in these soaps have an ionic character. The absorption maxima corresponding to the anti-symmetric vibration of carboxylate ion near $1650-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is not observed in the spectra of fatty acids, but the C=O stretching band appeared near 1700 cm^{-1} . The absorption maxima observed near $2660-2650$, $1700-1680$, $1449-1430$, $950-930$, 690 and 550 cm^{-1} corresponding to the OH groups in the spectra of fatty acids have disappeared in the spectra of alkali and lanthanum soaps. The absorption maxima observed near $940-930\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of these soaps are assigned to the deformation vibration of the carboxylate ion. The absorption maxima observed near 690 and 550 cm^{-1} in the spectra of fatty acids are assigned to the bending and wagging modes of vibrations of the carboxyl group of the acid molecule, respectively. The assigned frequencies are in agreement with the results of other workers^{9,10}.

Thermal analysis: The results of TGA show that the final residue is lanthanum oxide, as the weight of the residue is in agreement with the theoretically calculated weight of lanthanum oxide from the molecular formula of the soap. It is found that a white crystalline substance condenses at the cold part of the tube on heating the soap and it is identified as caprone (b.p. 228.0°) and laurone (m.p. 69.3°) in the case of caprate and laurate, respectively. The results of TGA have been explained by using Freeman-Carroll, Horowitz-Metzger and Coats-Redfern equations, and it is found that the decomposition reaction of lanthanum soaps is kinetically of zero order and the energy of activation for the decomposition process is $1-10\text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

X-Ray diffraction studies: The intensities of the diffracted X-rays as a function of the diffraction angle, 2θ , for lanthanum caprate and laurate are observed and the interplanar spacings, d , have been calculated from the positions of the intense peaks using Bragg relationship, $n\lambda = 2d \sin\theta$, where λ is the wavelength of the radiation.

A large number of peaks arising from the diffraction of X-ray by planes of metal ions (known as basal planes) have been observed over the range of $3-40^\circ$ of the diffraction angle in the diffraction patterns of lanthanum caprate and laurate. The appearance of diffractions upto 8th order for caprate and upto 9th order for laurate suggests good crystallinity for lanthanum soaps. The interplanar spacings for 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th and 8th order diffractions for lanthanum caprate are 30.00 , 29.46 , 29.65 , 29.54 , 29.90 , 29.43 and 29.19 \AA , respectively. The average planar distance, i.e. the long spacing for lanthanum caprate is 29.60 \AA . The interplanar spacings as calculated for lanthanum laurate for 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th order diffractions are 34.73 , 35.21 , 34.23 , 34.33 , 34.22 , 34.34 , 34.59 and 35.42 \AA , respectively, and

the average planar distance is 34.63 \AA . The difference in the long spacings of lanthanum laurate and caprate is 5.03 \AA which corresponds to double the length of methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) groups in the fatty acid radical constituent of these soap molecules. It is, therefore, suggested that the zigzag chains of fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules extend straightforward on both sides of each basal plane. The values of long spacings for lanthanum caprate (29.60 \AA) and laurate (34.63 \AA) are smaller than the calculated dimensions of caprate (32 \AA) and laurate (37 \AA) ions from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles, and this suggests that the molecular axes are somewhat inclined to the basal planes. The metal ions fit into spaces between oxygen atoms of the ionised carboxyl group without a large strain of the bonds.

The values of the long spacings for lanthanum soaps are in agreement with the double layer structure of soaps proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi¹¹, in which the metal ions are arranged in a parallel plane equally spaced in the soap crystal with fully extended zigzag chains of fatty acid radicals on both sides of each basal plane.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (A.S.G. and M.S.) are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowships.

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